

D3.5 – Advancing the use of visual systems to support older adults managing multiple chronic health conditions (Update)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAL Active and assisted living

ED Emergency Department

EM Experimental Medicine

EU The European Union

ESR Early stage researcher

FSCQ Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire

HCP Healthcare Professional

ICT Information and Communication Technologies

PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

RCT Randomised controlled trial

QoL Quality of Life

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is to provide the final update evaluation report on the use of camera-based technologies for older adults living at home with multiple chronic health conditions (multimorbidity), building on the work of the previous deliverable D3.4 submitted in M29. This deliverable provides details on research outcomes from ESRs 8 and 17 (who replaced ESR7) on how the respective ESR topics have advanced knowledge in 3 core areas:

- 1) Behaviour change theory to facilitate the design, development, and implementation of camera-based systems for active and assisted living. This builds on and finalises the initial work explored in D3.4 on the impact of visual systems on changing behaviour to improve disease management processes including multimorbidity (ESR 8).
- 2) Healthcare practitioners' (HCP) perspectives on the use of camera based technologies in telehealth for older adults living at home with chronic conditions or multimorbidity. The outcomes are based on a scoping review conducted to explore the breadth of current literature on the perceptions of HCPs towards the use of cameras in AAL and map out reported attitudes and perceptions in real-life settings (ESR17).
- 3) The evaluation of research outcomes from ES8 and 17 on end-users' privacy, data protection and ethical concerns for camera use within the home and implications for future camera-based AAL implementation and research. (ESR 8 and 17).

This deliverable begins with a brief summary of the previous deliverable, D3.4 (Section 1), to contextualise the research presented here. In Section 2, ESR 8 details the use of behaviour change theory and techniques to enhance older adults' acceptance of visual systems, while in Section 3, ESR17 will focus on the viewpoint of HCPs towards the application of camera systems to support self-management of people with chronic conditions or multimorbidity. Section 4 collectively reflects on the

privacy and ethical concerns extracted from the research of ESR 8 and ESR 17 regarding end-users' use of cameras in the home to support older adults including those managing chronic disease and multimorbidity. Section 5 discusses the implications of these findings for camera-based AAL implementation and future research. Finally, Section 6 provides the conclusion to the report.

As reported in D3.4, in agreement with the project officer, the PhD focus of ESR 9 was changed from the original grant agreement to focus on privacy-aware embodied intelligence for robots in assisted living environments (moving from an original focus on personalisation of self-management/education and training for individuals with multimorbidity using visual based data). While the research outcomes of ESR9 will advance the overall core aim of visuAAL (e.g. by improving research to the use of robots in home environments to support older adults) the technical focus of the work is no longer in line with the aim of this deliverable. Instead, the research of ESR9 is reported in D3.1 (Doctoral Theses M56). Finally, ESR 7 exited the programme in M38 (October 2022) and therefore their contribution is included in D3.4.

1. Introduction

1.1 Summary of D3.4

Deliverable 3.4 (M29) which is the precursor to D3.5 (M54), contextualised and reported preliminary outcomes of the research projects of ESRs 7 and 8. ESR 7 provided a review of the use of visual systems to support self-management activities for persons with chronic health conditions and multimorbidity focusing on technology acceptance, whilst ESR 8 reported on the initial research conducted on the application of behavioural change theory to the design, development, and implementation of camera systems for home-based active and assisted living (AAL). The report also provided a brief evaluation of strategies most appropriate to address end-user privacy and ethical concerns towards the use of camera-based AAL systems within the home.

1.2 Deliverable D3.5 overview

In line with the deliverable aims, this report provides an update to research progress since D3.4 (M29), focusing on the outcomes of ESR 8 and 17. As D3.4 already provides an overview of key definitions related to the work of ESRs 7, 8, and 17—including population ageing, ageing in place, active and assisted living, and camera-based AAL technologies—this information will not be repeated here.

In order to have a comprehensive overview of the use of visual systems to support older adults with multimorbidity at home, this deliver presents two key complimentary perspectives, firstly that of the older adult as the primary end user in the home and secondly of the healthcare professional (HCP) as the key individual in the older adults care network supporting them as part of their health and well-being journey. Thus, the work of ESR 8 focuses on the older adult user perspective - specifically, it examines and aims to intervene in the evaluation and acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies by older adults. Addressing older adult user acceptance is crucial as the potential benefits of these technologies for improved wellbeing and longevity may not be realised without acceptance. Importantly, the culmination of ESR 8's work—a “future-self intervention” (described in further detail in Section 2)—offers a useful means with which to address the user perspective by

promoting older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. This focus on the user perspective aligns well with ESR 17's focus on the perspective of healthcare professionals, (HCPs), as they play an important role in facilitating the adoption of technologies to support patient care. ESR 17's work maps out the reported attitudes and perspectives of HCPs regarding the use of cameras in telehealth, as well as explores the current use and role of camera-based technologies in the context of AAL for patients with multimorbidity or chronic disease with comorbidities. The remaining structure of D3.5 is as follows:

Section 2 focuses on the research of ESR8 which investigates the application of behavioural change theory to the design, development, and implementation of camera-based systems for home-based active and assisted living. In particular, ESR8 employs a specific research framework - i.e., the experimental medicine approach to behaviour change (Nielsen et al., 2018) — in an attempt to uncover behavioural targets that can be leveraged within interventions designed to increase older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies (hereafter referred to as “acceptance-facilitating interventions”). The section begins with an outlay of the wider motivating context undergirding ESR 8's PhD research, followed by a brief recapitulation of its broader and more specific research aims. Next, the research methodology à la the experimental medicine approach will be outlined, alongside a summary of emergent and preliminary research outcomes. Implications (including ethical) of the research for the broader agenda of camera-based AAL will be offered, followed by suggestions for fruitful avenues for future research.

Section 3 covers the research of ESR17 who joined the project in the final year (24/05/2024 – M45) focusing on HCPs perspectives on the use of camera-based technologies in telehealth for older adults living at home with chronic conditions or multimorbidity. Given a wide variety of technologies with new applications being constantly developed and applied in diverse settings for various needs (Flodgren et al., 2015), there's is a need to specifically assess the acceptability of video-based AAL solutions from the perspective of HCPs. Understanding their concerns, expectations and real-world applicability is crucial to ensuring successful integration into healthcare

practices that support older adults managing at home. Outcomes from the scoping review presented in this section, provide the first in-depth examination of this area. The section ends by outlining the implications for future research as well as ethical ethical considerations for camera and telehealth solutions within the home to support individuals managing their health and well-being.

Section 4 provides a summary of the deliverable.

2. Using behaviour change techniques and theory to increase older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies

2.1 Contextualising the present research

The sections below provide an update to the research by ESR 8 that was presented in D3.4. The previous deliverable outlined the value of behaviour change theory and techniques for increasing older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. It postulated the role of an established psychological construct - future self-continuity - in older adults' acceptance of said technologies. Specifically, it theorised that older adults with greater future self-continuity - that is, those who feel more similar to their future selves, or who imagine their future selves in more vivid and positive terms—may be more inclined to accept camera-based AAL technologies today. Across a series of studies, this conjecture was empirically tested and verified. The section below provides details of this research, offering a potential innovative behaviour change solution to increasing older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies.

2.1.1 The need for acceptance-facilitating interventions

As outlined in deliverable D3.4, the transformative potential of camera-based AAL technologies to secure safer, healthier, longer, and more independent lives for older adults is marred by stagnated diffusion of these technologies. This is primarily attributable to older adults' poor acceptance of these technologies (Demiris et al., 2004; Dermody et al., 2021; Kirchbuchner et al., 2015; Offermann-van Heek et al., 2019). Failure to remedy this state of affairs risks jeopardising the interventionist potential of camera-based AAL technologies. To date, little empirical attention has been directed at uncovering strategies to enhance older adults' acceptance of these technologies. Such scholarly efforts are important as the results of these investigations can fruitfully inform the content of acceptance-facilitating interventions to benefit the uptake and spread of camera-based AAL technologies. Therefore, to address this research gap, ESR 8's research aims to develop and evaluate the efficacy of an

intervention designed to increase older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. Additionally, it seeks to explore the underlying reasons or mechanisms that contribute to the intervention's efficacy. In pursuit of these aims, the PhD employed a stepwise approach in the manner of an established framework for developing and evaluating behaviour change interventions: the *experimental medicine* (EM) approach. The specific objectives of the PhD research were to:

1. To identify factors that influence older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, which can serve as targets for acceptance-facilitating interventions.
2. To identify measures of an identified target and examine whether variation in the target is associated with changes in acceptance.
3. To develop and optimise for older adults an intervention that incorporates manipulations to engage (i.e., elicit change in) the identified target.
4. To examine whether an intervention that incorporates the manipulations in Research Objective 3 leads to increased acceptance, and if this increase is mediated by changes in the target.

2.1.2 Future-self continuity as a putative target for acceptance-facilitating interventions

D3.4 provided brief insight into a potentially influential target for acceptance-facilitating interventions—future self-continuity. Future self-continuity can be understood as the subjective sense of connection that individuals feel between their present and the future selves (Sedikides et al., 2023). It is well established that future self-continuity has important implications for intertemporal decisions - decisions involving costs and benefits that manifest at different points in time (Bartels & Rips, 2010). This is because intertemporal decisions often pit an option with higher immediate benefits but lower long-term utility - that maximise utility for the current self - against an option with lower immediate benefits but higher long-term utility - that maximise utility for the future self (Bartels & Rips, 2010; Bartels & Urminsky, 2011;

Frederick et al., 2002). In effect, intertemporal decisions involve trading off the welfare of the current self for that of the future self (Bartels & Rips, 2010).

According to a *future self-continuity hypothesis*, the degree to which individuals discount the welfare of their future self should be scaled by the degree to which they feel disconnected from their future self (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009). To use a more intuitive analogy, if people consider their future self as a stranger, they may rationally have no more reason to save money for themselves than to give money to a stranger (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009). Conversely, people should be more willing to make immediate concessions to benefit a future self who is experienced as psychologically proximate. According to this line of theorising, individuals with lower continuity to their future self should be less willing to make present sacrifices in order to benefit their future self (Bartels & Rips, 2010; Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009; Hershfield, 2011). Indeed, this intuition has been validated empirically. Studies have demonstrated that people who report feeling more (versus less) connected to their future selves engage in more forward-looking behaviour including saving more for retirement (Hershfield, 2011), expanding greater academic effort and achieving better grades (Bixter et al., 2020), eschewing tendencies to procrastinate (Blouin-Hudon & Pychyl, 2015), exercising more (Rutchick et al., 2018), smoking less (Zhao et al., 2020), and taking more deliberate career-planning initiatives (Chishima & Wilson, 2021).

The behavioural impact of future self-continuity has potentially important implications for older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. This is because the decision to accept or reject camera-based AAL technologies is an intertemporal one. The decision to accept camera-based AAL technologies (or not) pits an option with smaller but sooner consequences such as invaded privacy and stereotyping "old age" imageries against an option with larger but later consequences such as overall improvements in health, wellbeing and longevity in the future. Acceptance thus requires that older adults defer benefits to, and endure costs on behalf of, their future selves. Yet, to the extent that individuals with poor future self-continuity care less about the welfare of their future selves (Bartels & Rips, 2010; Hershfield, 2011), they may be less willing to endure these costs and may ultimately decide to reject the technology.

2.2 Theorising and developing an acceptance-facilitating intervention

2.2.1 An experimental medicine approach to developing an acceptance-facilitating intervention

The abovementioned narrative underscores the empirical core of the PhD research. In a series of studies, ESR 8 set out to examine the extent to which future self-continuity can explain older adults' acceptance (or lack thereof) of camera-based AAL technologies, which in turn informed the development of an acceptance-facilitating intervention. This systematic structure to the research adopts an experimental medicine (EM) approach to behaviour change. The EM approach provides researchers with a structure for constructing a programme of research to uncover evidence-based strategies to change behaviour, most commonly via *behaviour change interventions* (Nielsen et al., 2018). The EM approach specifies four key steps in the intervention development pipeline:

1. **Identify** factors associated with the behavioural outcome of interest - in the case of this PhD research, the behavioural outcome is *acceptance* of camera-based AAL technologies. Factors identified as being associated with the behavioural outcome of interest (i.e., acceptance) constitute potential targets¹ for interventions designed to change the behaviour (i.e., acceptance-facilitating interventions).
2. **Validate** the target by examining associations between the target and the behavioural outcome of interest.
3. **Engage** the target through experimentation or intervention.
4. Conduct a **full test** of the proposed model through experimental procedures (e.g., randomised controlled trials) that determine the extent to which the intervention not only evoked a meaningful change in the behavioural

¹ Targets are analogous to the factors that influence the behavioural outcome of interest, representing the mechanisms of action through which interventions can change behaviour.

outcome of interest but does so through its ability to effect change in the identified target.

The EM approach lends utility to this research as it provides a structured method for isolating the optimal content of acceptance-facilitating interventions. By specifying the underlying linkages between intervention strategies, targets (i.e., mechanisms of action), and behavioural outcomes, the EM approach advances the development of robust acceptance-facilitating interventions with applicability to the camera-based AAL decision context and potentially broader AAL decisional context on the whole. Figure 1 depicts the stepwise procedure of the EM approach.

Figure 1: The experimental medicine (EM) approach to behaviour change.

The research of ESR8 therefore enacted a series of studies with adherence to the four steps in the EM approach. The first study was a scoping review of the barriers and facilitators to older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, which aligned with the first *identification* step in the EM approach (Path A; Figure 1). Aligning with the second *validation* step, the second study was a descriptive cross-sectional study of the association between future self-continuity and older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies (Path B; Figure 1). These studies and their results

are detailed more exhaustively in deliverable D3.4 and will therefore only be briefly summarised herein.

Based on the results of the scoping review, which found that older adults tended to defer their acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies into the future and onto other people, it was hypothesised that low continuity to the future self may account for non-acceptance of the technology. Presumably, this is because the concern that individuals have for their future selves is thought to be scaled by the degree to which they feel connected or continuous to their future selves, much the as they would feel more concerned for close others compared to distant strangers (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009; Hershfield, 2011). Therefore, to the extent that the decision to accept camera-based AAL technologies represents a farsighted choice made in the interests of the future self rather than the present self (as D3.4 elaborates in fuller detail), older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies may be similarly scaled by their degree of future self-continuity.

The above theorising received empirical support in the cross-sectional study presented in D3.4, which demonstrated that older adults with lower future self-continuity - specifically, those who saw their future selves in less vivid and less positive terms - were significantly less accepting of camera-based AAL technologies compared to those with higher future self-continuity. Furthermore, in line with theorising that future self-continuity promotes greater valuation of long-term outcomes due to the future self compared to short-term outcomes endured by the present self, the results of mediation analysis found that the positive effect of future self-continuity on acceptance was mediated by increased perceptions of the technology's usefulness - specifically, benefits to health, wellbeing, and longevity, which primarily accrue to the future self.

The results of the scoping review and cross-sectional study therefore successfully *identified* and *validated* future self-continuity as a potential target for acceptance-facilitating interventions, fulfilling the first two steps of the EM approach to behaviour change. Their results add credence to the hypothesis that future self-continuity constitutes a potential target, or mechanism of action, for changing technology acceptance behaviour. Specifically, a target can be understood as a

construct that is hypothesised to guide changes in behaviour (in the case of this research, acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies), and that in turn constitutes what the selected intervention strategy will aim to do to try to engage to change behaviour (in the case of this research, to increase acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies; Nielsen et al., 2018). Therefore, targeting future self-continuity in an intervention may prove a useful acceptance-facilitating strategy.

2.2.2 A brief review of “future-self interventions” and their applicability to AAL technology acceptance decisions

The results of the scoping review and cross-sectional study (see D3.4) provided solid empirical grounds to move forward with the next step of the EM approach—to *engage* future self-continuity through intervention. Specifically, the findings of the cross-sectional study suggested that interventions targeting improvements in the vividness and positivity with which older adults’ experience their future selves may prove beneficial for increasing their acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies.

Target engagement requires knowledge of strategies that can be used to manipulate the target in question. Yet, to date, no interventional attempts have been made in the domain of technology acceptance that aim to increase older adults’ future self-continuity. Nonetheless, a burgeoning line of research on the use of “future-self interventions” - interventions designed to enhance future self-continuity to catalyse forward-looking behaviour - lends useful insight and offer promise for informing the development of acceptance-facilitating interventions. These studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of various means of enhancing future self-continuity, including exposing people to age-progressed images or avatars of their future selves in virtual reality (Hershfield et al., 2011; Kuo et al., 2016; Sims et al., 2015; van Gelder et al., 2015), having people write letters to their future selves (Chishima & Wilson, 2021; Rutchick et al., 2018), or simply conjuring mental images of their future selves (Blouin-Hudon & Pychyl, 2015, 2017). Testifying to the potency of future self-continuity for increasing forward-looking behaviour, these interventions have yielded a variety of positive behaviour change outcomes including increased physical activity (Rutchick et al., 2018), healthy eating (Kuo et al., 2016), increased retirement savings (Hershfield

et al., 2011), improved career planning behaviour (Chishima & Wilson, 2021), reduced tendencies to procrastinate (Blouin-Hudon & Pychyl, 2017), and lower likelihoods of engaging in delinquent behaviour (van Gelder et al., 2015).

Notwithstanding the promise of the abovementioned future-self interventions for promoting forward-looking behaviour, the applicability of these interventions to the context of AAL-relevant decision-making is dubious. It is perhaps intuitive that it would be prohibitively costly - in terms of time and resources invested, for example - to have older adults confront their future selves in a virtual reality environment. It is difficult to envision how such an intervention may be transferrable to the context of deciding whether to accept camera-based AAL technologies; presumably such a decision would be made outside a virtual reality setting. Similarly, writing letters to the future self holds potency for changing behaviour but may not be feasibly achieved by older adults with poor manual dexterity. To this end, it behoved ESR 8 to identify or develop a means to increase future self-continuity that was broadly applicable to the AAL decision context and that could be feasibly implemented with older adults.

To this end, a novel study by Shah et al. (2022) was timely and pertinent. The researchers developed a future-self intervention that comprised a question-and-story exercise designed in the style of a Mad Lib². The intervention was a tablet-based application that first asked participants to answer a series of questions about their envisioned futures and future selves. Participants' answers were then piped into a personalised story about their future and future selves that they then read aloud. Figure 2 presents the original intervention. It was hypothesised that completing the question-and-story exercise would encourage more deliberate and vivid reflection on the future self, which would in turn increase future self-continuity and, accordingly, forward-focussed behaviour. In direct confirmation of this theorising, Shah et al. (2022) found that compared to a control group of participants, those who underwent the intervention

² A Mad Lib is a word game where players fill in blanks in a story with parts of speech (e.g., nouns, verbs, adjectives) without knowing the context, often resulting in a humorous or nonsensical narrative. The Shah et al. (2022) intervention followed a Mad Libs format but yielded a coherent, non-humorous narrative about the participant's future self.

were almost four times as likely to set up a direct debit to a voluntary retirement savings contribution.

Questions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client's name: 2. What is your age? 3. Client's gender: 4. Your name [the promoter's]: 5. What do you like doing in the evenings? 6. What do you like doing over the weekends? 7. Who is one person you like spending time with? [name and relationship] 8. About how many hours do you work per week? 9. When you are older, how many hours per week would you like to work, if any? 10. What would you like to do more of in the future when you are older? 11. Where would you like to live in the future? 12. Why there? 13. Who is one person you would like to spend time with in the future? [name and relationship] 14. Do you think it's important to take the necessary steps today in order to secure that future? [yes/no] 15. Currently, do you feel confident that you have already saved enough money to have the future you want? [yes/no] 	Text	<p>My name is [Maria] and I am [42] years old. Today is a special day because I am meeting with [Elena] preparing to have a good future. As part of this preparation process, it is important that I think about my current lifestyle and my future lifestyle.</p> <p>Currently, after work I like to [swim] and on the weekends I like to [bake pastries].</p> <p>One person I enjoy spending time with is my [husband], [Eric]. Currently, I work [50] hours a week. When I am older, I would like to work [5] hours a week and spend more time [playing the piano]. When I get older, I would like to live [in the mountains] because [I like to ski]. I also would like to spend more time with my [friend], [Ana]. In order to enjoy the lifestyle I want in the future, I will need money on a regular basis. Right now, it [is] important for me to be able to achieve this lifestyle.</p> <p>Currently, I [am not] confident that the money I have in my account or what I am saving will be enough to maintain the lifestyle that I want in the future.</p>
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Figure 2: Shah et al. (2022) question-and-story future-self intervention

The Shah et al. (2022) intervention (Figure 2) was germane to the purposes of ESR 8's research for several reasons. First, the structurally and stylistically simple format of the question-and-story exercise circumvents the more involved and cumbersome processes of engaging with a virtual reality environment or writing a physical letter. Furthermore, the digital (i.e., tablet-based) modality of the intervention can be feasibly implemented in an AAL-relevant decision context. For instance, physicians could conceivably present the intervention to older patients prior to making recommendations regarding the uptake of camera-based AAL technologies. The intervention can also be easily and quickly adapted to other digital mediums (e.g., desktop computer, mobile phones) to be embedded in marketing material relevant to the technology, such as websites on which camera-based AAL technologies might be advertised. Indeed, online interventions are eminent in their ability to be accessed ad hoc, to be continually modified and tailored, and to reach large audiences almost instantaneously in resource and cost-efficient ways (Murray, 2008). The utility and

aptness of an online intervention in this context are further buttressed by research demonstrating that older adults represent a large share of purchasers of online goods and services (Vroman et al., 2015). However, where necessary and preferable to suit particular contexts or audiences, the intervention could also be readily adapted to paper-and-pencil formats. Based on this line of reasoning, it was decided that the Shah et al. (2022) intervention would be suitably adapted to the present research.

2.2.3 Developing and optimising a future-self intervention for older adults

A qualitative intervention development and optimisation study

Using the original Shah et al.'s (2022) future-self intervention as a scaffold, a person-based approach to intervention development (Yardley et al., 2015) was used in the context of a qualitative study to adapt and optimise a future-self intervention for older adults. The study aimed to develop and optimise the intervention to suit the contexts, needs, and preferences of older adults and to better target the behavioural outcome of interest: acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. The study comprised two phases: an intervention adaptation phase followed by an intervention optimisation phase. Conduct of the study was approved by the Faculty of Health Sciences Ethics Committee, Trinity College Dublin.

Phase 1: Intervention adaptation

Adapting the original Shah et al. (2022) intervention was a necessary research endeavour because the original intervention was targeted at an entirely different behavioural outcome - to increase retirement savings behaviour among adults of working age. The original intervention contained questions such as: "When you are older, how many hours per week would you like to work, if any?" and "Currently, do you feel confident that you have already saved enough money to have the future you want?". Though apt to encourage future-relevant contemplation among working-age individuals, these questions may be weakly applicable to the older adult context. Research on subjective ageing - how individuals perceive their own ageing (Westerhof et al., 2014) - has revealed numerous domains in which individuals assess their own ageing and, accordingly, their aged future selves. For example, studies have outlined several important life domains that older adults consider relevant to, and that require

preparation for, their future old age. These do not solely revolve around financial and employment-related considerations (as exemplified by Shah et al.'s (2022) intervention) but also involve facets of life such as personality, social relationships, mental and physical fitness, housing, emergency situations, appearance, health, and leisure activities. Therefore, it was necessary to adapt the content of the original intervention to better suit the contexts of older adults, as well as to capture the multidimensionality of subjective ageing.

As a first step, the content of the original Shah et al. (2022) intervention was adapted to yield a prototype future-self intervention. The prototype intervention took the form of a question-and-story exercise embedded in an online Qualtrics survey, and was therefore accessible on desktop, mobile, or tablet computers. Extracting from the literature details on the ways in which older adults think about their future selves (Kornadt et al., 2015; Kornadt & Rothermund, 2011, 2014), the questions were designed to compel thinking across life domains with demonstrable importance for older adults' futures, including personality, lifestyle, social relationships, employment, health, housing, and emergency situations (Kornadt et al., 2015; Kornadt & Rothermund, 2014). Sample questions included: "What do you like doing [in the daytime/over the weekends]?", "Is it important to you that you can continue doing these things in the future, when you are older?", "In the future, where would you want to live?", "Why there?", "How would you feel if you [lived in a nursing home/remained living at home] in the future?". A corresponding Mad Libs-style story was created to align with the developed question set. Figure 3 presents the adapted future-self intervention.

1. What is your first name?
2. What is your age in years?
3. What is one value that is important to you today? (for example, being honest, reliable, organised, etc.)
4. When you are older, will being [value] still be important to you?
5. What do you like doing in the daytime?
6. What do you like doing over the weekends?
7. Is it important to you that you can continue doing these things in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
8. How would you feel if you were not able to keep doing the things that you enjoy when you are older?
9. What is the first name of one person you like spending time with?
10. What is this person's relationship to you?
11. Would you like to continue spending time with this person in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
12. Currently, you would say your health is... [Poor/Fair/Good/Very good/Excellent]
13. In the future, you would want your health to be... [Poor/Fair/Good/Very good/Excellent]
14. Do you have any chronic conditions now? [Yes/No]
15. How would you feel if your health declined in the future?
16. In the future, do you wish to be able to help yourself and manage life well on your own? [Yes/No]
17. How would you feel if you had to depend on others for help in the future?
18. Do you think that there is a risk that you could experience a fall in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
19. In the future, where would you want to live? [In my own home/In a nursing home]
20. Why there?
21. How would you feel if you lived in a nursing home in the future?
22. How would you feel if you remained living at home in the future?
23. Is it important to you that you can continue living at home in the future? [Yes/No]
24. Do you think there is a risk that you might not be able to live the life that you want in the future? [Yes/No]
25. [If "Yes" to question 24] Do you think you can lower this risk by taking the necessary steps today? [Yes/No]
26. The actions you take today will ensure you can live the kind of life you want in the future. Do you agree or disagree? [Agree/Disagree]
27. Currently, do you feel confident that you are on the path to achieving the future that you want? [Yes/No]

(a)

My name is [Conan] and I am [61] years old. Today is a special day because I have been thinking about preparing for a good future. As part of this process, it is important that I think about my current lifestyle and my future lifestyle.

I am someone who values being [funny]. In the future, when I am older, being [funny] will be [equally as important] to me.

I like to spend my days [chatting] and I enjoy [hiking] on the weekends. I [would] like to be able to keep doing these things when I am older. If I am not able to keep doing these things, I would feel [hopeless].

Currently, I enjoy spending time with my [friend], [Matt], and I [would] like to continue doing so in the future.

Currently, I would say that I am in [good] health, and I would like to have [fair] health when I am older. [However, I suffer from chronic conditions]. If my health became worse in the future, I would feel [upset].

In the future, I [want] to be able to help myself and manage life on my own. If I had to depend on others for care, I would feel [depressed]. [I know that there is a risk of me experiencing a fall when I am older, which would lower my ability to be independent].

In the future, I would want to live [in my own home] because [I love my home]. If I had to move to a nursing home in the future, I would feel [despondent]. If I remained living in my own home, I would feel [capable]. It [is] important to me that I can remain living at home when I am older.

Right now, I feel like there [is a] risk that I may not be able to have the future that I want. [I know that I can lower this risk by taking the necessary steps for my health today]. I [know] that the actions I take today will decide the life I live in the future.

(b) Currently, I [am not] confident that I am on the path to achieving the future that I want.

Figure 3: (a) Question set and (b) future-self story contained in the prototype future-self intervention, adapted from Shah et al. (2022).

Phase 2: Intervention optimisation

Following the adaptation of the original intervention, a mixed-methods person-based protocol was employed to ascertain the views of older adults on the relevance, acceptability, feasibility, usability, and behaviour change efficacy of the prototype intervention. These insights were systematically incorporated into the intervention using a Table of Changes approach (described below) to optimise the intervention's potential behaviour change efficacy.

Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants from an older adult participant panel at NetwellCASALA³, a research centre based at the Dundalk Institute of Technology (DkIT) that specialises in research to facilitate independent living for

³ <http://www.netwellcasala.org>

older adults. Individuals were invited to participate if they were aged 60 to 80 years, community-dwelling (i.e., not living in residential care, assisted living, or other long-term care settings), and capable of using a tablet or desktop computer independently. Research suggests that a sample size of $n = 5$ participants is sufficient to uncover 80% of usability issues using qualitative procedures, with additional participants yielding progressively diminishing information (J. Nielsen, 1994). Therefore, the final sample size of $n = 7$ participants was appropriate. Potential participants were contacted through a gatekeeper at NetwellCASALA and were provided with information on the study along with an informed consent and an expression of interest form. Participants who responded with an expression of interest were then contacted by the researcher (ESR 8) to schedule a study session. Sessions were held at NetwellCASALA at a time convenient to participants.

At the start of each study session, participants received instructions about the study before signing an informed consent form. Participants were then directed to a tablet containing the online Qualtrics survey. They then completed a demographic questionnaire (indicating their age, gender, race/ethnicity, education, employment status, current annual income, self-reported chronic disease status) before completing pre-intervention measures of future self-continuity and acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies.

Future self-continuity was assessed using three items drawn from the Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire (Sokol & Serper, 2019). The items assessed the perceived similarity between the present and the future self (How similar do you currently feel to yourself 10 years from now?"; 6-point Likert scale: 1 = completely different, 6 = exactly the same), the vividness with which the future self is envisaged ("How vividly do you picture this self 10 years from now?"; 6-point Likert scale: 1 = not at all, 6 = perfectly), and positivity towards the future self ("How much do you like this self 10 years from now?"; 6-point Likert scale: 1 = not at all, 6 = perfectly). Acceptance was assessed using a three-item scale adapted from Hennemann et al. (2016): "I would like to try the camera-based home monitoring technology", "I would use a camera-based home monitoring technology if offered to me", "A camera-based home

monitoring technology would be worth paying for” (5-point Likert scale: 1 = totally disagree; 5 = totally agree). After completing these measures, participants completed the prototype future-self intervention, followed by post-intervention measures of future self-continuity and acceptance. Future self-continuity and acceptance were assessed pre- and post-intervention as a means of examining whether completing the future self-intervention led to changes in these constructs.

Following the completion of the intervention, participants underwent retrospective one-on-one semi-structured interviews with the researcher. Adhering to a semi-structured interview guide, participants were asked for their overall experience of using the intervention, their likes and/or dislikes, the ease of using the intervention, and any suggestions they had for improving the intervention. If participants exhibited pre-intervention to post-intervention change in scores on the measures of future self-continuity and/or acceptance, they were asked for their opinions on why this change occurred, and key intervention elements that supported change. Conversely, for those who did not exhibit changes, participants speculated possible reasons for this lack of change and suggested modifications to enhance the intervention's effectiveness in promoting future self-continuity and acceptance. Further questions gleaned participants' opinions on other domains they thought were relevant to their futures that were not captured in the intervention. All interviews were audio recorded and transcribed verbatim.

Adhering to the person-based approach to intervention development (Yardley et al., 2015), an iterative approach to data analysis was undertaken involving cyclical moves between data collection, analysis, intervention modification, and further data collection until data saturation was achieved. ESR 8 read and familiarised herself with the interview transcripts before collating quotes pertaining to positive and negative aspects of the intervention into a “Table of Changes” (Bradbury et al., 2018). Modifications were made to the intervention where they were deemed easy to implement, likely to enhance the intervention's acceptability, feasibility, usability, engagingness, or likely to influence improvements in future self-continuity and/or acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. Interviews continued alongside data

analysis to enable iterative changes to the intervention, and modified interventions were then tested in subsequent interviews with new participants. Data saturation was achieved when no further modifications were deemed necessary (Bradbury et al., 2018). Figure 4 presents a flow diagram of the intervention optimisation study procedure.

Figure 4: Flow diagram of intervention optimisation study procedure.

Data was analysed using a mixed-methods approach that incorporated both qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative methods included a Table of Changes analysis (described above) which examined participants' feedback to inform iterative

refinements to the intervention for improved relevance, acceptability, usability, and engagingness. Additionally, thematic analysis was undertaken to understand participants' perspectives of the intervention's effects on future self-continuity and acceptance. Quantitative analysis included formal statistical assessments of the changes (or lack thereof) in participants' future self-continuity and acceptance scores from pre- to post-intervention.

2.2.4 Results

A total of $n = 7$ participants (57.1% male, mean age = 71.7 years, range = 63–79 years) were recruited. The majority of participants were retired (85.7%), had completed third-level education (57.1%), and had been diagnosed with at least one chronic disease (85.7%). All participants were Caucasian. Interviews lasted between 25 and 43 minutes.

On the whole, participants responded positively to the prototype future-self intervention. Four main themes were identified relating to the barriers and facilitators to engaging with the intervention. These included overall positive views on the intervention's usability and understandability, acceptability, relevance to older adults, and engagingness. These themes are summarised briefly in the following section.

Qualitative findings

Theme 1: Usability and understandability

Participants were unanimous in their opinion that the intervention was easy to use and understand. Most participants agreed that the tablet-based (or desktop-based) modality of the intervention was amenable to older individuals, and many appreciated the simplicity of the rudimentary text-based format of the question-and-answer exercise:

"It was it was good, because it was simple. It was in your, in your face. Do you know? So, people who wouldn't be as cute as me with tablet usage? They'd still able to do it fine." – **Participant 1**

“Yes. I must say, I think that your system is very good. I like that.” –

Participant 2

“Yeah, well as in even things like the font size was good. You know, and the font style, it was very, it wasn't fussy, it was very clear font. And, yeah, it's good.”

– **Participant 6**

“Very easy to understand. Some of them not so easy to answer. You just have to, as I say, the challenge. Think. That's, that's why I don't like box ticking exercises.” – **Participant 2**

Theme 2: Acceptability

Most participants saw the intervention as acceptable to themselves and to other older individuals. The questions were seen as engaging but unintrusive, compelling pertinent thinking about one's future in ways that did not perturb or agitate:

“They weren't too probing...they were what I would call surface questions.”

– **Participant 2**

“I think that it's clever in the sense that you capture the information that you want, in a non-probing way.” – **Participant 2**

Noteworthy, however, were comments relating to how the intervention evoked negative emotions due to its ability to prompt (potentially unwanted) contemplation about ageing. Some participants alluded to the unpleasantness of confronting their own ageing, and wanted as far as possible to avoid such future contemplation:

“Whilst I was putting it together I didn't like it [...] That part of it then that says: Well, this is going to be me, mm, I don't like that part [...] Who's going to like it, you know?” – **Participant 5**

“Yeah. Great. Great. I feel great. But it's, it's when I read about the thought of going into a nursing home, you know...that's absolutely, sorry. Absolutely no.” – **Participant 6**

Nonetheless, other participants appreciated how the intervention prompted them to contemplate their futures. To these participants, the recognition of one's own mortality was an important catalyst for ageing-related preparation - that is, those thoughts and activities about how to age well that are taken in preparation for later life. To these participants, the intervention was not seen as aversive or offensive; instead, it was framed as a pertinent trigger for timely forms of thinking and future-relevant preparation:

“No, because that's, that's not because of the design... It's because of my answers. You know... I suppose it's my issue to deal with, isn't it? And it did trigger it, but no, no, no, not at all.” – Participant 6

“As far as I'm concerned, the first step is, we're not going to be here forever. That's it. It's a fact. That's it - accept it. And once you've accepted it, the rest of it comes easy [...] I think that exercise, you know, it's impactful, the idea of the shots of, you know, the, the idea of the fall [...] I think that that would certainly be a turning point. For people to say, oh, maybe it's not such a bad idea after all.” – Participant 2

Theme 3: Relevance

The questions posed to participants and the resultant future-self story was seen as relevant to participants and to older adults more generally. Many participants thought that the intervention captured the elements most poignant when thinking about, and preparing for, later life:

“The questions are very relevant. And very, you know, there is merit and everything that was there for a question and then for an answer, absolutely.” – Participant 5

“That's, that's it. That's me...I think it captures me. And I that's what you're trying to do. And you've done it.” – Participant 2

“I found that it captured exactly... I mean as I read it back, I read the story back with the idea it will say, oh, that's me.” – Participant 2

Theme 5: Engagingness

Participants on the whole appreciated the personalised and almost quasi-interactive nature of the intervention, commenting that it forced them into cogent and timely forms of thinking about ageing and the future. Participants though that completing the intervention was an enjoyable process and particularly liked the personalisation of their own “future self-story”, seeing this as a poignant and evocative piece of imagery.

Others liked that the intervention was not a simple “box-ticking” exercise but rather allowed them the freedom to think about their visions of and desires for their own futures, which manifestly was not a typical day-to-day activity:

“What I liked about it was that you were forced to think.” “You know, it wasn’t just an ABCD exercise.” – Participant 2

“Yeah, it got a little part of the... REM eh, was, was reactivated. Got me thinking on it slightly, you know.” – Participant 5

“Very good, I was going to say, did I do that? You know. I thought it was brilliant. I thought I was gonna be an author, you know.” – Participant 5

Theme 4: Modifications to the intervention

Although the intervention was overall received positively by participants, several suggestions were made about changes that could be made to the intervention to improve its acceptability, usability and understandability, relevance to older adults, and engagingness. A series of amendments and refinements were made to the intervention based on these suggestions. These included minor changes to the questions to make them more relevant to older adults (e.g., asking them about activities they enjoy doing during the day rather than during the evening), and the inclusion of additional questions to probe other life domains seen as relevant to older adults’ futures and future selves. Examples of these modifications are presented in Table 1 and the final future-self intervention is presented in Figure 5.

Table 1: Table of Changes—Summary of main changes (and non-change) to the future-self intervention.

Suggested change	Rationale for change	Change made
The question “What is one thing you enjoy doing in the evening?” should be changed to “What is one thing you enjoy doing in the day?”	“Because...as you grow older, evenings are going to be a time where you're not going to be as anxious to go out because you're going to have crowds or whatever.” – <i>Participant 4</i>	The question was modified to state “What is one thing you enjoy doing in the day?”
Questions about the future and future self should probe aspects related to current and/or future employment	“Because [work is] a huge part of a person’s role, and it is the one thing that is likely to change the most for people”; “For so many people...their identity is caught up with, with work” – <i>Participant 6</i>	Additional questions were included that were drawn from Shah et al. (2022): “About how many hours do you work per week, if any?”; “When you are older, how many hours per week would you like to work, if any?”
The question “The actions you take today will ensure you can live the kind of life you want in the future. Do you agree or disagree?” had a “Yes/No” binary response option that was seen as difficult to answer on account of its dichotomous nature.	“It's very, it's sort of the statement, the actions you take today will ensure you, like absolutely, that will be brilliant if it was that easy. You know what I mean?” – <i>Participant 6</i>	Question was removed following team-wide discussion as it was deemed inessential to the intervention’s goal of encouraging contemplation on the future self.

1. What is your first name?
 2. What is your age in years?
 3. What is one value that is important to you today? (for example, being honest, reliable, organised, etc.)
 4. When you are older, will being [value] still be important to you?
 5. What do you like doing in the evenings?
 6. What do you like doing over the weekends?
 7. Is it important to you that you can continue doing these things in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
 8. How would you feel if you were not able to keep doing the things that you enjoy when you are older?
 9. What is the first name of one person you like spending time with?
 10. What is this person's relationship to you?
 11. Would you like to continue spending time with this person in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
 12. About how many hours do you work per week, if any?
 13. When you are older, how many hours per week would you like to work, if any?
 14. What would you like to do more of in the future when you are older?
 15. Currently, you would say your health is... [Poor/Fair/Good/Very good/Excellent]
 16. In the future, you would want your health to be... [Poor/Fair/Good/Very good/Excellent]
 17. Do you have any chronic conditions now? [Yes/No]
 18. How would you feel if your health declined in the future?
 19. In the future, do you wish to be able to help yourself and manage life well on your own? [Yes/No]
 20. How would you feel if you had to depend on others for help in the future?
 21. Do you think that there is a risk that you could experience a fall in the future, when you are older? [Yes/No]
 22. In the future, where would you want to live? [In my own home/With my adult child/Children/In an assisted living facility or a continuing care residence/In a nursing home]
 23. Why there?
 24. How would you feel if you lived in a nursing home in the future?
 25. How would you feel if you remained living at home in the future?
 26. Is it important to you that you can continue living at home in the future? [Yes/No]
 27. Do you think there is a risk that you might not be able to live the life that you want in the future? [Yes/No]
 28. [If "Yes" to question 27] Do you think you can lower this risk by taking the necessary steps today? [Yes/No]
 29. Currently, do you feel confident that you are on the path to achieving the future that you want? [Yes/No]
- (a)

My name is [Conan] and I am [61] years old. Today is a special day because I have been thinking about preparing for a good future. As part of this process, it is important that I think about my current lifestyle and my future lifestyle.

I am someone who values being [funny]. In the future, when I am older, being [funny] will be [equally as important] to me.

I like to spend my evenings [chatting] and on the weekends, I enjoy [hiking]. I [would] like to be able to keep doing these things when I am older. If I am not able to keep doing these things, I would feel [hopeless].

One person I enjoy spending time with is my [friend], [Matt], and I [would] like to continue doing so in the future. Currently, I work [40] hours a week. When I am older, I would like to work [10] hours a week and spend more time [with my children].

Currently, I would say that I am in [good] health, and I would like to have [excellent] health when I am older. [I do not suffer from chronic conditions]. If my health became worse in the future, I would feel [upset].

In the future, I [want] to be independent and to manage life on my own. If I had to depend on others for care, I would feel [depressed]. [I know that there is a risk of me experiencing a fall when I am older, which would lower my ability to be independent].

I want to live [in my own home] in the future because [I love my home]. If I had to move to a nursing home in the future, I would feel [despondent]. If I remained living in my own home, I would feel [capable]. It [is] important that I can remain living at home in the future.

Right now, I feel like there [is a] risk that I may not be able to have the future that I want. [I know that I can lower this risk by taking the necessary steps for my health today].

(b) Currently, I [am not] confident that I am on the path to achieving the future that I want.

Figure 5: (a) Question set and (b) future-self story contained in the final future-self intervention.

Quantitative findings

Paired samples *t*-tests indicated no significant change in future self-continuity scores from pre-intervention ($M = 3.05$, $SD = 1.01$) to post-intervention ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 1.15$), $t(6) = -.826$, $p = .441$. This change was of low practical significance, with a Cohen's *d* value of $-.312$, indicating a small effect size. Similarly, no significant change was observed in participants' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies from pre-intervention ($M = 3.05$, $SD = 1.25$) to post-intervention ($M = 2.86$, $SD = 1.27$), $t(6) = 1.92$, $p = .103$, Cohen's *d* = 0.726 .

2.2.5 Discussion

The evidence collated from the semi-structured interviews enabled an in-depth understanding of participants' experiences with a novel future-self intervention, as well as their needs and preferences when using such an intervention. Overall, participants indicated that the intervention was acceptable, easy to use and understand, engaging, and relevant to older adults. Participants' comments did not indicate the need for major upheavals to the intervention's semantic content or mechanisms of action. The intervention was feasibly implemented with older adults ranging from 60 to 80 years of age, with the digital intervention modality (online questionnaire) presenting no difficulty to participants. However, participants had useful recommendations for changes that could be made to improve the intervention. Following discussion within the wider research (i.e., supervisory) team, appropriate changes were incorporated into the intervention.

Important to this research programme, individuals aged 60 to 80 are a key demographic group impacted by multimorbidity: studies have indicated a prevalence of 65% experiencing multimorbidity among older adults aged 65 to 84 (Barnett et al., 2012). Furthermore, a recent systematic review found that more than half of individuals aged below 60 experience multimorbidity (Chowdhury et al., 2023). The future-self intervention may therefore have particular utility for persons with multimorbidity, potentially benefitting their acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies designed to support self-management of chronic disease and multimorbidity (e.g., Andreu et al., 2016).

Despite the null findings that arose from formal statistical analyses regarding the intervention's impact on future self-continuity and acceptance, these findings should be interpreted with caution given the small sample size ($n = 7$) of the present study. Furthermore, the pre-post design of the study precludes inferences about causal effects of the intervention. The primary aim of the study was to adapt and optimise a future-self intervention that could be feasibly implemented among older adults; efficacy, albeit of interest, was of secondary importance.

The overarching result of this study was an online future-self intervention that was optimised for acceptability, usability, feasibility, and engagingness among older adults. The likely benefit of this optimised intervention is enhanced effectiveness in increasing future self-continuity and/or acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. Results of the study successfully fulfilled the third *engagement* step of the EM approach, which spells out the need to define strategies to sufficiently elicit change in the target, future self-continuity. The results provided the foundation with which to pursue the next step of the EM approach, which is detailed below.

2.3 Testing the effect of an acceptance-facilitating intervention

2.3.1 A randomised controlled trial of the effects of the future-self intervention on acceptance

The results of the qualitative intervention development study (Section 2.2 above) provided the grounds to move forward with the fourth step of the EM approach - to conduct a full test of the proposed behaviour change model by examining whether engaging the target (i.e., future self-continuity) leads to behaviour change. In the context of this study, this full model test involved an examination of the effect of the developed future-self intervention on older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies.

To achieve the above, a randomised controlled trial (RCT) of the effect of the future-self intervention was conducted. The RCT is the method of choice for assessing the efficacy of behaviour change interventions, as it enables causal inferences about not only the effect of the intervention on the behavioural outcome of interest, but also sheds light on the mechanisms of action through which the intervention exerts these effects (Sheeran et al., 2017). In the context of this research, an RCT would allow conclusions on the effect of the future-self intervention on acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies as well as conclusions on whether this effect can be attributed to changes in future self-continuity. The research embarked on the next stage of the EM approach to behaviour change by conducting an online RCT of the effect of the developed future-self intervention on older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL

technologies. The primary aim of the study was to examine the intervention’s effect on acceptance. Its secondary aim was to examine whether future self-continuity (and its separable similarity, vividness, and positivity subcomponents) mediated the effect of the intervention on acceptance.

2.3.2 Study design and participants

The study was an RCT with a parallel-group design hosted on the online survey platform Qualtrics. Eligible participants were community-dwelling older adults aged 60 to 80 years. The minimum age of 60 years aligns with the United Nations’ operationalisation of an older adult as any individual aged 60 and over (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Population Division, 2015). The upper age limit of 80 years was established to exclude the individuals in the “oldest old” category—those aged 80 and above (Erlangsen et al., 2004)—as it was anticipated that individuals at this age would face challenges in envisioning and assessing their future selves over a 10-year horizon while completing the Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire (described below). Participants were recruited from the online crowdsourcing platform Prolific Academic⁴. The conduct of the study was approved by the Faculty of Health Sciences Ethics Committee, Trinity College Dublin.

2.3.3 Measures

Future self-continuity

The 10-item Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire (FSCQ; Sokol & Serper, 2019) was used to assess participants’ future self-continuity. Responses to the FSCQ yield an overall score of future self-continuity as well as subscale scores corresponding to each of the three established subcomponents of future self-continuity: similarity to the future self (6-point Likert scale: 1 = completely different, 6 = exactly the same),

⁴ Prolific Academic (<https://www.prolific.com/>) is an online platform designed to facilitate high-quality data collection for academic research. It was used in this research to efficiently gather survey responses from a pre-screened and diverse participant pool.

vividness of the future self (1 = not at all, 6 = perfectly), and positivity towards the future self (1 = not at all, 6 = perfectly).

Self-rated health

Two items measured participants' self-rated health in general ("In general, would you say your health is...?") and in comparison to other people ("Compared to others, would you say your health is...") on 5-point Likert scales (1 = poor; 2 = fair; 3 = good; 4 = very good; 5 = excellent).

Privacy concerns

After reading a descriptive paragraph about camera-based AAL technologies and their purported benefits for health, safety, and independence in old age, participants completed a 4-item measure, adapted from Jaschinski et al. (2021), assessing their privacy concerns regarding the technology. Sample items included the statements: "If I use the camera-based technology, I worry that my personal information might be shared with others without my permission"; "Using the camera-based technology will feel like an invasion into my personal space" (5-point Likert scale; 1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). The scale demonstrated good internal reliability, with a Cronbach's α of .900.

Perceived usefulness

The perceived usefulness of camera-based AAL technologies was assessed using a 7-item scale also adapted from Jaschinski et al. (2021). Sample items included the statements: "If I use the camera-based technology, I will feel safer in my home"; "Using the camera-based technology will allow me to age in my home environment" (5-point Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree; Cronbach's α = .911).

Attitude towards camera-based AAL technologies

Participants rated their attitude towards camera-based AAL technologies along six bipolar objectives (good-bad, wise-foolish, valuable-worthless, like-dislike, pleasant-unpleasant, enjoyable-unenjoyable). The question stems and adjectives were taken from Jaschinski et al. (2021). This scale demonstrated satisfactory internal

reliability, with a Cronbach's α of .921. Higher scores on the measure indicate more positive attitudes towards camera-based AAL technologies.

Acceptance

Behavioural intention to use camera-based AAL technologies was used as a proxy for acceptance (Cimperman et al., 2016; Jaschinski et al., 2021). A four-item scale (Cimperman et al., 2016) asked participants to rate their agreement with statements such as "Assuming I had access to a camera-based home monitoring technology, I intend to use it" and "I intend to use a camera-based home monitoring technology in the near future" (7-point Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree; 7 = strongly agree).

2.3.4 Procedure

A link to an online Qualtrics survey was advertised on Prolific to eligible participants. Once they clicked on the link, participants were re-directed to the Qualtrics survey where they read information on the study and provided informed consent. Following the completion of demographic items, a Qualtrics randomiser facilitated the experimental manipulation, where participants were randomly allocated 1:1 to a control (no intervention) group or an experimental group where they completed the future-self intervention. Next, all participants completed measures of future self-continuity, self-rated health, privacy concerns regarding camera-based AAL technologies, perceived usefulness of the technology, attitude towards the technology, and acceptance of the technology. Participants received £1 for completing the survey, which is in line with Prolific's payment standards.

2.3.5 Results

A total of $n = 181$ eligible responses were collected. Participants had a median age of 64, were approximately evenly split in terms of gender (54.7% female, 45.3% male) and employment status (53.6% unemployed, 46.4% employed), and were highly educated with the majority having attained a tertiary education (53.6% tertiary and beyond, 46.4% up to secondary). The sample was disproportionately Caucasian

(92.3% Caucasian, 7.7% non-Caucasian) and free from chronic disease (74.0% without chronic disease, 26.0% with chronic disease).

Bivariate correlations

Correlations between all study variables of interest are presented in Table 2. Acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies was positively associated with perceived usefulness of and attitude towards the technology and negatively associated with privacy concerns. Acceptance was positively associated with FSCQ-vividness, but no associations with FSCQ, FSCQ-similarity, or FSCQ-positivity were observed.

Table 2: Bivariate correlations between study variables of interest.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. FSCQ	-						
2. FSCQ-Similarity	.797***	-					
3. FSCQ-Vividness	.776***	.359***	-				
4. FSCQ-Positivity	.861***	.525***	.582***	-			
5. Perceived usefulness	.073	.054	.037	.086	-		
6. Privacy concerns ^a	.079	.089	.045	.095	-.404***	-	
7. Attitude	.111	-.003	.162*	.127	.698***	-.508***	-
8. Acceptance ^a	.106	-.003	.154*	.107	.593***	-.489***	.811***

Note: Values are raw, untransformed data. Correlations are as Pearson's r and Spearman's ρ for parametric and ^anon-parametric data, respectively. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Between-group differences on acceptance and secondary outcome measures

Self-reported acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies did not differ between control (log-transformed mean = .341, $SD = .295$) and intervention (log-transformed mean = .357, $SD = .258$) groups, $t_{179} = -.389$, $p = .698$. Additionally, no significant differences were observed between the intervention and control group on privacy concerns ($t_{179} = .690$, $p = .491$; $U = 4002.5$, $p = .792$), perceived usefulness ($t_{179} = .548$, $p = .585$), or attitude towards camera-based AAL technologies ($t_{179} = .482$, $p = .631$). Between-group differences did not achieve significance for FSCQ ($t_{179} = -1.29$, $p = .198$), FSCQ-similarity ($t_{179} = -1.84$, $p = .068$), FSCQ-vividness ($t_{179} = -.075$, $p = .940$), or FSCQ-positivity ($t_{179} = -1.24$, $p = .216$).

Moderation analyses

Exploratory moderation analyses were conducted to ascertain whether demographic factors moderated the effect of the future-self intervention on acceptance. Indeed, an unadjusted moderation model revealed a significant group allocation*age interaction effect on acceptance ($B = -.210$, $SE = .081$, $p = .011$). Simple slopes analyses revealed a significant positive effect of allocation to the intervention group on acceptance among younger-old participants aged < 65 years ($B = .121$, $SE = .057$, $p = .037$) but no effect in participants aged ≥ 65 years ($B = -.089$, $SE = .058$, $p = .122$). Results of moderation analyses were unaltered when adjusted for the covariate race/ethnicity. Further exploratory models revealed no other demographic moderator of intervention effects on acceptance.

Mediation analyses

Mediation analyses were conducted to uncover potential mechanisms of action underpinning the effect of the future-self intervention on acceptance. Specifically, exploratory mediation models estimated the extent to which the effect of the future-self intervention on acceptance was transmitted through future self-continuity or similarity, vividness, and/or positivity subcomponents of future self-continuity.

Mediation results revealed a significant indirect effect of the future-self intervention on acceptance through future self-positivity in participants aged < 65 years. Allocation to the intervention (versus control) group was positively associated with increased FSCQ-positivity scores ($B = .488$, $SE = .192$, $p = .012$). Consistent with full mediation, when acceptance was simultaneously regressed on both FSCQ-positivity and group allocation, only FSCQ-positivity emerged as a significant predictor of acceptance ($B = .096$, $SE = .043$, $p = .033$); the effect of group allocation on acceptance was no longer significant ($B = .113$, $SE = .071$, $p = .109$). Bootstrapping estimates confirmed full mediation: the bias-corrected confidence interval for the indirect effect was strictly positive ($B = .047$, 95% CI [.005, .126]). A covariate-adjusted model yielded statistically similar results. Figure 6 graphically depicts the results of the mediation analysis.

Figure 6: Path coefficients for (a) unadjusted and (b) covariate-adjusted mediation models predicting acceptance from group allocation through FSCQ-positivity. Coefficients represent unstandardised regression weights. FSCQ = Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

2.3.6 Discussion

Results of the randomised controlled study testify to the benefits of a future-self intervention for increasing the acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, but only in those aged 65 years and below. The findings further illustrate the mechanism of action through which the future-self intervention exerted its effects: exposure to the intervention increased the positivity with which older adults' orient towards their future selves, which in turn increased their acceptance of the technology.

It is unclear why the effects of the future self-intervention were confined to the younger-old aged below 65 and failed to generalise to those aged 65 and above. Ceiling effects on future self-continuity (Löckenhoff & Rutt, 2017) and/or acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies (Beach et al., 2009; Offermann-van Heek et al., 2019) are plausible explanations. Nonetheless, the results of the present study usefully illustrate an acceptance-facilitating strategy that has potent benefits for a specific demographic segment. Specifically, our findings suggest that a brief online future-self intervention, consisting of a simple question-and-answer exercise designed to prompt

greater elaboration on and contemplation of one's future self, is enough to enhance acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies in those aged 65 and below. Mediation results further testify to the utility of targeting positive future self-views for enhancing acceptance. Therefore, cohering with the EM approach, the present results demonstrate successful *engagement* of the target, future self-continuity, and offer promising mechanistic results derived from a *full test* of the proposed behaviour change model.

2.4 General Discussion

2.4.1 Integrated summary of research findings

ESR 8's research addressed the practical problem of older adults' resistance to camera-based AAL technologies, marking the first known attempt to mitigate this resistance using behaviour change theory and techniques. Through stringent adherence to an established framework for behaviour change - the EM approach - it hypothesised and ultimately validated a new target for acceptance-facilitating interventions - future self-continuity. In specifying and evaluating the role of future self-continuity in acceptance, it demonstrated that the vividness and positivity with which older adults experience their future selves play a significant role in their acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. As such, interventions targeting these constructs could inform the core of future acceptance-facilitating interventions. Research in this regard might fruitfully explore the value of other future-self interventions - for example, interventions that aim to enhance future self-continuity by exposing individuals to images of their future selves (e.g., Hershfield et al., 2011) - for improving older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies.

The potential impact of future-self interventions may extend beyond camera-based AAL technologies to other types of AAL technologies, including non-visual systems. This broader applicability stems from the nature of the decision to accept AAL technologies, which often involves a conflict between present and future interests. For example, accepting an AAL technology often involves immediate challenges such as financial investment, the need to learn new skills, and potential stigma associated

with technological assistance. These costs largely accrue to the present self. By contrast, the long-term benefits of acceptance such as improved health, wellbeing, and longevity, may be predominantly enjoyed by the future self. Therefore, in as much as individuals with lower future self-continuity tend to prioritise the interests of their present self, compared to those of their future self (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009; Hershfield, 2011), they may be more inclined to reject AAL technologies. Future research should aim to validate this theoretical proposition and explore its practical application to the acceptance decisions rendered for other (e.g., camera-less) types of AAL technologies. Future studies may also fruitfully explore the acceptance-facilitating efficacy of our future-self intervention in the context of other technologies.

2.4.2 Implications

The value of the future-self intervention

The accumulated findings add to the still nascent literature on strategies to enhance the acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies and importantly pinpoint an intervention target that has to date evaded the literature on technology acceptance. This is because theorising on technology acceptance has predominantly focused on more pragmatic factors with influence on technology acceptance, namely, the perceived usefulness and perceived ease-of-use of the technology (Davis, 1989). Although lowering physical barriers to using technology is arguably a crucial step to increasing individuals' acceptance of the technology, leveraging psychological barriers to acceptance is an overlooked but promising means of intervention. This is because overcoming physical barriers to acceptance typically necessitates more involved, resource-intensive processes such as designing easier-to-use technologies and user interfaces, upskilling and training potential users, and so forth.

By contrast, although a question-and-answer exercise targeted at modulating individuals' views of their future selves offers an ostensibly rudimentary intervention, it may nevertheless have pronounced effects for increasing acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. In fact, it is precisely this rudimentary quality that makes the future-self intervention amenable to being implemented across populations and contexts. For instance, the intervention could easily be embedded within online

marketing material targeted at potential older users of camera-based AAL technologies. Alternatively, the intervention could be implemented—either in a digital or paper-and-pencil format—in care settings where the technology might be introduced to potential users. Indeed, research indicates that AAL technologies are typically introduced to older adults through channels such as verbal recommendations by staff or healthcare professionals in independent living residences (Berridge, 2014) and local community centres (Vincent et al., 2006). Additionally, online catalogues allow suppliers of AAL technologies to advertise their products for potential users to explore (e.g., AAL Products, n.d.). A future-self intervention could potentially be integrated into the user journey through these online catalogues. This intervention might influence older adults' decision-making processes regarding AAL technology acceptance. The future-self intervention is thus eminent in its novelty and adaptability, and our findings lend preliminary support for its utility in supporting the widespread dissemination of camera-based AAL technologies. The approach presented in this research thus addresses the fundamental decision-making process underlying technology acceptance, rather than focusing solely on the features of specific technologies.

Although future self-positivity emerged as the predominant mechanism of action underpinning the effect of the future-self intervention, it is noteworthy that future self-vividness—the vividness with which individuals envisage their future selves—exhibited significant positive correlations with acceptance at the whole-group level. This result was replicated in the correlational results of the cross-sectional study previously reported in D3.4, where future self-vividness was strongly and positively associated with acceptance. This suggests that interventions targeting future self-vividness may have potent benefits for improving acceptance among older adults more generally and not just those aged 65 and below. It may, therefore, be instructive for future studies to investigate whether other means of engaging future self-continuity—for instance, strategies aimed at increasing the vividness with which future selves are envisaged—may benefit the acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies among older adults on the whole.

Ethical implications of the future-self intervention

The ethical implications for this work also warrant consideration. While important for social and economic ends, there are important ethical issues implicated in the development and implementation of acceptance-facilitating interventions that require careful consideration.

By seeking to increase acceptance, this research attempts to narrow the gap between “undesirable” behaviour (non-acceptance) and “desirable” behaviour (acceptance). Although this behaviour change aim is supported by narratives emphasising the potential of camera-based AAL technologies to promote individual and societal welfare (Colantonio et al., 2018), the extent to which such “gaps” between “undesirable” and “desirable” behaviour warrant narrowing is questionable.

Behaviour change interventions, such as the one created and evaluated in this thesis, are frequently associated with the political philosophy of “libertarian paternalism”. Paternalism refers to using interventions to steer behaviour in a welfare-promoting direction, and libertarian refers to implementing interventions in ways that preserve freedom of choice (Gane, 2021; Thaler & Sunstein, 2003, 2008). The use of “nudges”—nonmonetary and nonregulatory interventions that affect behaviour without limiting options or drastically changing economic incentives—is a defining characteristic of libertarian paternalism (Halpern, 2015; Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). Nudges operate by altering the external context in which decisions are made, referred to as the “choice architecture” (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). For example, choice architecture manipulations such as reducing the sizes of plates (Wansink, 2004) or placing healthier items at eye level (Cadario & Chandon, 2020) have been successfully used to nudge healthier food choices.

Although effective for changing behaviour, nudges have been critiqued on account of restricting individuals’ freedom of choice and undermining their authentic will. For example, defaulting individuals to a smaller plate size exploits the human tendency towards inertia; when presented with a default option, people typically stay with the default (Sunstein, 2014). People who are nudged in this way might not be aware that interventions are changing their behaviour, which makes it challenging to act in the opposite direction of what the nudge is trying to encourage (Banerjee et al.,

2024; Grüne-Yanoff, 2012). In the plate-size example, people don't have a clear reason for selecting the smaller plate, and although they can pick differently, it may require substantial mental effort to do so (Van Gestel et al., 2021). As a result, a common ethical accusation against nudges is that they work by "manipulating people's choices" (Hansen & Jespersen, 2013, p. 5), taking advantage of psychological processes in ways that undermine autonomy and make it more difficult to oppose the nudge's desired result.

Importantly, while the future-self intervention attempts to change behaviour—from a position of non-acceptance and non-adoption to a position of acceptance and adoption—it possesses several features that help it evade the ethical critiques levelled against nudge interventions. Specifically, the future-self intervention can be characterised as a “boost” (Hertwig & Grüne-Yanoff, 2017) rather than a nudge, steering behaviour in ways that uphold or improve—not undermine, as a nudge would do—people’s capacity to make their own decisions. While nudges use cognitive and motivational biases (like inertia) to change behaviour, boosts work to build on preexisting competencies or introduce new ones, enabling people to make decisions that support their own objectives (Hertwig & Grüne-Yanoff, 2017). Additionally, boosts are entirely transparent to the decision-maker: boosted individuals are aware of the strategies being used to encourage behaviour change and can thus choose whether or not to apply them (Grüne-Yanoff, 2018; Hertwig & Grüne-Yanoff, 2017). For example, while a nudge that aims to increase retirement savings behaviour might enrol individuals into a retirement savings plan by default, boosts may employ less “manipulative” strategies such as teaching simple financial heuristics or rules of thumb (Drexler et al., 2014) to encourage retirement savings behaviour.

Notably, our developed future-self intervention can be conceived as a boost (rather than a nudge) to acceptance. This is because the intervention does not undermine individuals’ ability to behave in ways that favour their present self—i.e., counter to the intervention’s intended direction. Instead, the intervention simply augments their ability to psychologically connect with their future selves, leaving them free to select which self to prioritise. As such, it avoids many of the moral criticisms

raised against nudge interventions. In our intervention structure, older adults' authentic will serves as the compass for behaviour. In order to determine whether or not to embrace the technology, older persons must actively participate in the intervention, such as by responding to the questions about the future and reading the future-self story out loud. Correspondingly, they are free to reject the technology if they so wish. In such ways, the behaviour change that results from exposure to the intervention is entirely a product of older adults' authentic will and decision-making competency rather than a compelled artefact of the choice architecture.

2.5 Conclusion

ESR 8's research project aimed to develop and evaluate the efficacy of an intervention to increase older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, and to examine the mechanisms underpinning its efficacy. As older adults are a key demographic impacted by multimorbidity (Barnett et al., 2012) and camera-based AAL technologies are a potential support for multimorbidity self-management (Andreu et al., 2016), the results of this work stand to inform strategies to improve individuals' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful multimorbidity self-management.

With adherence to a structured methodological framework for behaviour change—the EM approach—ESR 8's research identified a novel psychological target for one such acceptance-facilitating intervention. The intervention proved successful in increasing acceptance of camera-based technologies to support health and wellbeing as well as independent living among older adults aged 65 and below. Specifically, it increased acceptance among this cohort by increasing the positivity with which older adults orient towards their future selves. The results of this research provide fruitful grounds for exploring the utility of the future-self intervention for other behaviour change endeavours, such as its potential application to increase individuals' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies as well as AAL technologies more generally. Usefully, the intervention evades important ethical charges commonly levelled against behaviour change interventions by focusing on improving rather than undermining individuals' capacity to decide for themselves what choice to make

following exposure to the future-self intervention; older adults are free to choose which self (e.g., their future self or their present self) in their AAL acceptance decision.

Overall, the developed future-self intervention offers a useful adjunct to more commonplace acceptance-facilitating strategies, such as the use of identity-redacting privacy filters of camera streams. Such complementary approaches, implementing interventions that target both practical (e.g., privacy concerns, usability issues) and psychological (e.g., poor future self-continuity) barriers to acceptance may hold substantial behaviour change potency, constituting a fruitful avenue for future research and implementation of camera systems to support older adults managing their health and well-being supported by their care network (e.g. family, caregivers, healthcare professionals).

3. Healthcare Professionals Perspectives on the Use of Camera Technologies in Telehealth

3.1. Overview to the research

This section presents the outcomes of the research conducted by ESR17, who undertook a scoping review to explore healthcare professionals' (HCPs) perceptions of camera-based telehealth technologies in the context of managing older adults with chronic conditions or multimorbidity. The study was driven by a notable gap in Active-Assisted Living (AAL) research, which has largely overlooked HCPs' insights despite their critical role as both key stakeholders and end-users of telehealth technologies. As end-users, HCPs directly interact with these systems in their clinical practice, and their acceptance, experiences, and feedback are pivotal to the successful implementation and integration of telehealth solutions. Understanding HCPs' perspectives is essential for developing tailored telehealth solutions that align with the needs of both patients and providers. By addressing this gap, the research provides valuable insights into the benefits, challenges, and ethical considerations surrounding camera-based telehealth technologies. These findings aim to inform future research and innovation in this field, ultimately supporting the broader adoption of such technologies in healthcare systems to better support individuals, namely older adults, self-managing their health (including chronic disease and multimorbidity) and wellbeing at home.

3.2. Introduction

3.2.1 Context of the research

Our current society faces a dual challenge: a rapidly aging population and a critical shortage of healthcare professionals (HCPs) (The Lancet Global, 2023; Wilmoth et al., 2023). This confluence creates a pressing issue—an ever-increasing demand for healthcare services amidst already strained resources. In practice, this results in longer wait times, overwhelmed emergency departments (EDs), and increased pressure on primary care providers (Government of Ireland, 2024; Lang-Hodge et al.,

2025; Savioli et al., 2022). Access to optimal healthcare is thus globally compromised, particularly for older adults living in remote or underserved areas (WHO, 2023). These challenges were further exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic, which exposed the fragility of public health systems and disrupted care provision for chronic diseases (Chudasama et al., 2020; Skou et al., 2022). Combined with workforce shortages, these trends have significant implications for healthcare delivery, particularly for older adults who often face complex health needs and multimorbidity (Doyle et al., 2019; Ho et al., 2022).

Globally, multimorbidity affects more than half of individuals aged 60 years and older, with a prevalence of 37.2% reported in systematic reviews. However, these figures may be underestimated in low-income countries due to limited reporting and fewer publications (Chowdhury et al., 2023). Despite its high prevalence, managing multimorbidity remains a significant challenge for both patients and HCPs. Patients must navigate complex care routines involving symptom monitoring, medication management, multiple healthcare visits, and communication with various providers. These demands can be overwhelming and highlight the need for innovative solutions to improve care delivery and patient autonomy (Doyle et al., 2019).

3.2.2 The role of telehealth in modern healthcare delivery

One promising solution lies in telehealth technologies, which facilitate healthcare delivery through information and communication technologies (ICT) to overcome geographical barriers (WHO, 2022). Telehealth covers a wide range of services, from prevention and education to diagnosis, treatment, and research (Eswaran H, 2022). Within this field, Active-Assisted Living (AAL) systems have emerged as key innovations designed to support ageing in place. These systems promote independence and safety for older adults through ICT-based solutions (Blackman et al., 2016; Calvaresi et al., 2017). AAL technologies include wearables monitoring devices with camera-based sensors or ambient intelligence, and mobile health tools (Fadrique et al., 2020). By enabling older adults to live autonomously at home, these systems have the potential to significantly improve

quality of life (QoL) for older adults while reducing reliance on formal healthcare services.

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of telehealth technologies such as video consultations, underscoring their utility in maintaining healthcare delivery while minimising risk of virus transmission (OECD, 2023). This trend highlights the potential for broader adoption of camera-based AAL technologies in home-based care. Camera systems offer diverse applications such as remote monitoring of health parameters, fall detection, rehabilitation support, and early detection of cognitive decline or frailty (Cardinaux et al., 2011; T. Mujirishvili et al., 2023; Tham et al., 2023). However, their acceptability depends on factors such as privacy concerns, security measures, usability, and the context of implementation (Koh et al., 2021; Lam et al., 2022; Peek et al., 2016). For instance, webcams used for video consultations are generally well-received and considered comparable to phone calls in terms of acceptability (Byambasuren et al., 2023) whereas surveillance cameras for home monitoring tend to raise concerns about intrusiveness (Maidhof et al., 2023).

3.2.3 HCPs as End-Users and Influencers in Telehealth

HCPs play an important role in facilitating the adoption of technologies to support patient care (Affinito et al., 2022). As key stakeholders in digital health implementation and conveyors of information to patients, their perspectives significantly influence technology acceptance and integration into clinical practice (van Tilburg et al., 2024). Despite their importance in shaping the successful adoption of telehealth solutions in practice, existing research disproportionately focuses on patient satisfaction with these services while neglecting clinicians' viewpoints. According to recent systematic reviews, only a small fraction of studies (15.5%) examine HCP perspectives on telehealth compared to those focused on patients (77.5%) (Hoff & Lee, 2022; OECD, 2023). Addressing this gap and presenting the views of HCPs is therefore of importance, given they are not only end-users but also decision-makers who can influence how these technologies are implemented and accepted in real-world settings.

ESR17's scoping review aimed to address this gap by mapping the existing literature on HCPs' perceptions of camera-based AAL technologies for older adults with chronic conditions or multimorbidity. The review sought to explore current applications, benefits, and challenges associated with these technologies while identifying knowledge gaps to inform future research directions.

3.3. Methods

The scoping review was conducted in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews (Aromataris et al., 2024). The results were reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR). Please see D3.1 for full details of the review.

The search strategy aimed to locate both published and unpublished studies. To ensure thorough coverage of the existing literature, the search was conducted on 20th September 2024 by the first author (KT) across four major relevant databases: CINAHL, APA PsycInfo (EBSCO), MEDLINE (PubMed), and Embase. A comprehensive search strategy for each database was developed using keywords found in the titles, abstracts, and subject headings of relevant articles. With guidance from an expert subject librarian, a broad five-concept search strategy was formulated to include keywords and subject headings related to the following concepts:

1. Camera-based technologies
2. Telehealth
3. AAL/ Aging in Place
4. Older adults with chronic conditions or multimorbidity
5. HCPs perceptions

Following the search, titles and abstracts were screened against predefined inclusion criteria by two independent reviewers, with full-text screening conducted subsequently. Reference lists of included sources were also reviewed to identify additional relevant studies. Disagreements during the selection process were resolved

through discussion with a third reviewer. Reasons for exclusions at each stage were recorded and are reported in the review (Tanaka et al., 2025).

To enhance comprehensiveness, *Research Rabbit*, an AI-driven literature discovery tool, was used to complement traditional database searches. The process involved creating a collection of seed articles from the primary search, reviewing the first 50 “similar works” suggested by the tool, and assessing their relevance based on inclusion criteria.

Data extracted from the included studies were compared and discussed between the same two independent reviewers (Kentaro Tanaka – ESR 17 and Tamara Mujirishvili – ESR 15) to reach consensus on the final dataset. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise study characteristics, while a basic qualitative content analysis was conducted using *NVivo 14* to identify and describe HCPs’ reported attitudes and perceptions of camera-based technologies. An inductive approach was employed, allowing themes to emerge organically without relying on pre-existing frameworks, which facilitated the identification of new or unexpected findings related to the types and applications of camera-based technologies in Active-Assisted Living (AAL).

3.4 Results

3.4.1 Search results and study selection

The search identified 345 records, with 62 duplicates removed. After title and abstract screening of 283 articles, 48 full-text papers were assessed for eligibility, resulting in the inclusion of 12 studies. Citation searching of these included studies identified 2 additional articles reporting relevant data from already-included studies. No articles suggested by *Research Rabbit* met the eligibility criteria. The detailed study selection process is illustrated in the PRISMA flowchart (Figure 7).

Figure 7: PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow diagram.

3.4.2 Characteristics of Included Studies

The included studies were published between 2008 and 2021 and reported data from six high-income countries: the United States (n=6; 50%), Australia (n=2; 17%), Canada (n=1; 8%), New Zealand (n=1; 8%), Norway (n=1; 8%), and Sweden (n=1; 8%). Study designs varied, with qualitative methods being the most common (n=6; 50%), followed by quantitative (n=5; 42%) and mixed methods (n=1; 8%). Data collection methods included interviews (n=5; 42%) and questionnaires (n=4; 33%), with three studies also incorporating focus groups to explore HCPs' experiences with camera-based technologies. The characteristics of the 12 included studies are summarised in Table 3

Table 3: Characteristics of included studies

Author/s (et al.)	Year of publication	Country	Study design	Data collection method/s	HCP speciality
Day et al.,	2016	New Zealand	Mixed method study	Questionnaire	Physician (MD)
Fincher et al.	2009	USA	RCT	Questionnaire	Nurse
Goldberg et al.	2021	USA	Qualitative research	Interview	Physician (MD)
Hinman et al.	2017	Australia	Qualitative research	Interview	Physiotherapist
Kalicki et al.	2021	USA	Cross sectional study	Survey	Physician (MD)
Kozikowski et al.	2019	USA	Qualitative research	Interview; Focus groups	Nurse; Physician (MD)
Kristoffersson et al.	2011	Sweden	Non-randomised experimental study	Questionnaire	Nurse; Occupational therapist; Other: Audiology
Mammen et al.	2017	USA	Qualitative data analysis from a RCT	Survey	Physician (MD)
Read Paul et al.	2019	Canada	Qualitative research	Questionnaire; Focus groups	Nurse; Physician (MD)
Solli & Hvalvik	2019	Norway	Qualitative research	Interview; Web forum content (online posts in a closed telecare network)	Nurse
Tieman et al.	2016	Australia	Cohort study	Survey; Interview; Focus group	Nurse
Wakefield et al.	2008	USA	RCT	Audiotape of telephone/videophone interaction	Nurse

RCT: Randomised Controlled Trial

3.4.3 Participant Characteristics

The most represented professions among participants were medical doctors (MD) and nurses, each of which was included in six studies. These professions accounted for 50% and 32% of the participants, respectively. Across all included studies, a total of 181 HCPs participated, with sample sizes ranging from 3 to 48 per study. However, most studies lacked detailed demographic data, such as age or sex, limiting the ability to describe the basic characteristics of participating HCPs. From the data available, the overarching profile of HCPs is predominantly female. A detailed description of the study population is provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Study population

Author/s (et al.)	Year of publication	HCP Characteristics									
		Age			Female n(%)	Nurse n (%)	MD n (%)	PTn (%)	OTn (%)	Other n (%)	HCP (Total) n=181
		Range	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)							
Day et al.,	2016	-	-	-	-	0 (0)	3 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3
Fincher et al.	2009	-	-	-	-	4 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4
Goldberg et al.	2021	25 - >65	-	37.5 (34-44.5)	27 (56)	0 (0)	48 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	48
Hinman et al.	2017	27-52	39 (9)	-	4 (50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	8 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	8
Kalicki et al.	2021	-	-	-	-	0 (0)	16 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	16
Kozikowski et al.	2019	-	-	-	-	-	-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	12
Kristoffersson et al.	2011	-	54 (2.85)	-	32 (91.4)	22 (63)	0 (0)	0 (0)	-*	13 (37)	35
Mammen et al.	2017	-	-	-	-	0 (0)	20 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	20
Read Paul et al.	2019	-	-	-	-	12 (86)	2 (14)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	14
Solli & Hvalvik	2019	44-70	-	-	5 (80)	6 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6
Tieman et al.	2016	-	-	-	10 (83)	11 (92)	1 (8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	12
Wakefield et al.	2008	-	-	-	3 (100)	3 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3

SD : Standard Deviation ; IQR : Interquartile Range ; MD : Medical Doctor ; PT : Physiotherapist ; OT : Occupational Therapist

*Included in 'Other'

3.4.4. Types of Technology and Modes of Use

The included studies reported on various types of cameras used in telehealth for managing older adults with chronic diseases or multimorbidity. Most studies employed consumer-level cameras, with webcams being the most commonly used (58%, n=7) (Goldberg et al., 2021; Hinman et al., 2017; Kalicki et al., 2021; Kozikowski et al., 2018; Mammen et al., 2018; Read Paul et al., 2019; Solli & Hvalvik, 2019). Tablets with built-in cameras were used in 50% of studies (n=6) (Day et al., 2016; Goldberg et al., 2021; Hinman et al., 2017; Kalicki et al., 2021; Kozikowski et al., 2018; Tieman et al., 2016), while smartphones appeared in 25% (n=3) (Goldberg et al., 2021; Kalicki et al., 2021; Kozikowski et al., 2018). Two older studies utilised videophones for telecommunication purposes (Fincher et al., 2009; Wakefield et al., 2008). One study uniquely reported on a robot equipped with a camera specifically designed for telehealth applications (Kristoffersson et al., 2011).

All included studies primarily used cameras to facilitate communication between healthcare professionals and patients. Figure 8 illustrates the types of cameras used and their purposes over time, while an overview of the included studies is provided in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Mapping of studies

From inner to outer circles: country, health profession, health context, technology type, purpose of use, authors. MD: Medical Doctor; PT: Physiotherapist; OT: Occupational Therapist.

3.4.5 Reported Attitudes and Perspectives

The analysis identified four overarching themes regarding HCPs' attitudes and perspectives on camera-based technologies in telehealth:

1. **Benefits and Satisfaction:** HCPs highlighted several benefits of video technology, including its relational and psychosocial value, which helped establish therapeutic bonds with patients when in-person visits were not possible (Collier et al., 2016; Day et al., 2016; Goldberg et al., 2021; Hinman et al., 2017; Mammen et al., 2018). The visual component provided additional context for clinical decisions through non-verbal cues and home environment observations (Kozikowski et al., 2018; Read Paul et al., 2019). Video consultations also saved travel time, with studies reporting an average of 1.5 hours saved per visit, improved accessibility for remote patients, streamlined workflows, and facilitated timely interventions (Day et al., 2016; Read Paul et al., 2019; Tieman et al., 2016). Overall, most HCPs expressed satisfaction with videoconferencing as an effective communication tool (Solli & Hvalvik, 2019; Tieman et al., 2016).
2. **Integration with Existing Care:** Telehealth was predominantly viewed as a supplement to traditional care rather than a replacement. Some HCPs emphasised that telehealth is “not for everything,” functioning mainly as an adjunct to usual care (Day et al., 2016). Its use varied by specialty, with geriatricians and primary care physicians more likely to substitute in-person visits, while emergency physicians used it to complement face-to-face consultations (Goldberg et al., 2021). Nurses recognised telehealth as a valuable tool for both current and future practices (Solli & Hvalvik, 2019). However, limitations were noted in contexts like home care, where video platforms could not fully replace in-person evaluations of environmental factors such as lighting or spatial layout (Collier et al., 2016).
3. **Technical Challenges:** Technical issues such as poor audio or video quality and unreliable internet connections were frequently reported barriers (Collier et al., 2016; Goldberg et al., 2021; Hinman et al., 2017; Kalicki et al., 2021; Mammen et al., 2018; Read Paul et al., 2019; Tieman et al., 2016). These disruptions frustrated both patients and providers, limiting the effectiveness of telehealth consultations.

4. **Concerns and preferences:** Ethical and legal concerns included ambiguity around accountability for patient care and access to sensitive data (Kozikowski et al., 2018; Read Paul et al., 2019). Clinical limitations, such as the inability to perform physical contact or thoroughly assess home environments, raised apprehensions about the adequacy of care provided remotely (Kozikowski et al., 2018; Mammen et al., 2018; Tieman et al., 2016). Additional challenges included increased workload from adapting to telehealth platforms, managing data notifications, and addressing accessibility issues caused by digital literacy gaps or financial constraints (Goldberg et al., 2021; Kalicki et al., 2021; Solli & Hvalvik, 2019). Some HCPs expressed a preference for in-person visits over video consultations due to their perceived impersonal nature, noting that patients often preferred physical presence for examinations (Kozikowski et al., 2018; Kristoffersson et al., 2011).

Table 5 summarises the eighteen identified codes, which are organised into the above-mentioned themes.

Table 5: Reported attitudes and perspectives

Themes and subthemes	References
Benefits and Satisfaction	
Added value of video technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relational and psychosocial benefits (Day et al.,2016 ; Hinman et al.,2017; Mammen et al.,2017 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Solli &Hvalvik, 2019; Tieman et al.,2016 ; Kristoffersson et al.,2011) • Saved travel times and improved accessibility (Hinman et al.,2017 ; Mammen et al.,2017 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Kozikowski et al.,2019 ; Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Tieman et al.,2016 ; Kristoffersson et al.,2011) • Visualization is significantly useful (Fincher et al.,2009 ;Hinman et al.,2017 ; Kristoffersson et al.,2011 ;Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Tieman et al.,2016) • Better insights enabling informed clinical decision-making (Day et al.,2016 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Kozikowski et al.,2019) • Facilitated early intervention (Day et al.,2016 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Tieman et al.,2016) • Provides a sense of security (Solli & Hvalvik, 2019; Tieman et al.,2016)
HCP's overall satisfaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall most HCP were satisfied with telehealth use (Fincher et al.,2009 ; Mammen et al.,2017 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Tieman et al.,2016 ; Kristoffersson et al.,2011) • Effective communication and patient management (Fincher et al.,2009 ; Mammen et al.,2017 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Wakefield et al.,2008 ; Tieman et al.,2016)
Integration with existing care	
Telehealth as an adjunct to usual care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telehealth is seen as an adjunct to usual care (Day et al.,2016 ; Hinman et al.,2017 ; Goldberg et al.,2021; Solli & Hvalvik,2019; Tieman et al.,2016)
Technical challenge	
Technical issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor audio, video or internet connection lead to frustration and sense of limited evaluation (Hinman et al.,2017; Mammen et al.,2017 ; Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Tieman et al.,2016 ; Kalicki et al.,2021)
Concerns and preferences	
Increased burden in practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenging and/or altered clinical care to overcome barriers to telehealth use (Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Solli & Hvalvik,2019) • Additional work and responsibility due to unfiltered influx of data notifications from the technology (Kozikowski et al.,2019)
Accessibility issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited accessibility for certain users due to factors such as insufficient digital literacy, cognitive or sensory impairments, or financial constraints (Goldberg et al.,2021 ; Kalicki et al.,2021)
Clinical limits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to physically touch (Mammen et al.,2017 ; Kozikowski et al.,2019 ; Tieman et al.,2016) • Incomplete assessment of home environment due to technological limitation (Tieman et al.,2016)
Medico-legal concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambiguity of responsibility and to who has access to data (Read Paul et al.,2019 ; Kozikowski et al.,2019) • Medico-legal concerns over remote assessment without physically putting hands on the patient (Tieman et al.,2016)
Preference favoring in-person visits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video-consultations are perceived as impersonal (Kozikowski et al.,2019 ; Kristoffersson et al.,2011)

3.5 Discussion

3.5.1. Comparative Insights: Contextualising Key Findings in relation to existing literature

The perspectives identified in this review align with findings from other studies on telehealth, revealing generally positive experiences with video consultations while highlighting significant challenges and barriers. HCPs reported benefits such as improved care coordination, time efficiency, and strengthened provider-patient relationships, consistent with prior studies (Bennell et al., 2022; Ezzat et al., 2023). Similarly, high satisfaction levels among physiotherapists using telehealth have been noted in other research (Bennell et al., 2022).

Challenges identified in this review also reflect those reported in recent studies. Rettinger and Kuhn (2023) scoping review highlighted barriers such as the inability to perform physical examinations, unreliable internet connections, limited technology access, and low digital literacy. These findings align closely with this review's identified challenges, including technical issues, limited accessibility, and the inability to provide hands-on care. Franzosa et al. (2021) similarly noted both benefits (e.g., improved patient triage and scheduling capacity) and barriers (e.g., reliance on caregivers, patients' cognitive or sensory impairments, and incomplete examinations) to telehealth implementation.

Interestingly, Franzosa et al. (2021) emphasised the importance of combining commercial and consumer-level technologies—such as FaceTime—for effective telehealth delivery. This aligns with this review's findings that consumer-level devices like webcams and tablets are widely used in telehealth. However, more advanced technologies, such as environmental camera systems or specialised tools for older adults, were largely absent from the included studies, except for one robot-based camera used in a pre-smartphone era study (Kristoffersson et al., 2011). This absence might reflect a broader gap in research addressing HCPs' needs for integrating advanced telehealth tools.

The shift from older technologies like videophones to consumer devices such as smartphones and tablets reflects a broader trend of healthcare consumerism (Taylor, 2019). Familiarity with these devices appears to facilitate HCPs' adoption of telehealth platforms (Goldberg et al., 2021; Solli & Hvalvik, 2019), reducing the learning curve and enhancing usability. However, inadequate training remains a barrier; Malliaras et al. (2021) found that many clinicians felt unprepared to deliver telehealth effectively. Additionally, some HCPs perceived video consultations as less personal than in-person visits, echoing findings from Kristoffersson et al. (2011) and Kozikowski et al. (2018) where patients were also noted to prefer physical presence during examinations.

These findings suggest that increased familiarity with telehealth tools—through prior exposure or training—may be key to improving HCPs' confidence in adopting video telehealth services and enhancing patient perceptions of its value.

Video-based telehealth emerges as a particularly valuable tool for addressing the complex care needs of older adults with multimorbidity. Doyle et al. (2019) highlighted a critical issue faced by persons with multimorbidity (PwM): frequent non-attendance due to the overwhelming burden of managing multiple appointments often scheduled on different days within the same week. This challenge is particularly true for those lacking informal caregiver support, as the effort involved in traveling to these appointments can be substantial (Doyle et al., 2019). In this context, telehealth presents a promising solution by reducing the need for travel and potentially improving appointment attendance rates.

In addition to logistical barriers, technological issues pose significant challenges in care delivery for older adults with multimorbidity (Collier et al., 2016; Goldberg et al., 2021; Hinman et al., 2017; Kalicki et al., 2021; Mammen et al., 2018; Read Paul et al., 2019; Solli & Hvalvik, 2019). Guise and Wiig (2017) reported that many HCPs perceive older adults as struggling with technology, citing difficulties in learning new skills or adapting to unfamiliar platforms. While some HCPs expressed optimism about older adults' ability to adapt to simple technologies, others argued that even these solutions might not suffice for certain individuals. Despite these concerns, Chen et al. (2022) identified successful strategies implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic that demonstrate how telehealth can effectively complement face-to-face care when thoughtfully implemented. These strategies include preparing for visits in advance, adapting to sensory needs, involving caregivers, and offering additional educational resources. Several studies included in ESR 17's scoping review (Collier et al., 2016; Day et al., 2016; Goldberg et al., 2021; Solli & Hvalvik, 2019) similarly suggest that telehealth is regarded by HCPs as a supplementary tool rather than a replacement for traditional in-person care. As healthcare systems continue to evolve, the integration of camera-based telehealth solutions may play a crucial role in supporting older adults with multimorbidity by offering flexible, accessible care options that complement traditional healthcare models. Future research should explore how HCPs interact with telehealth technologies and identify strategies to better integrate digital solutions into healthcare without compromising quality of care. There is a particular need for studies that specifically examine the challenges of managing multimorbidity and consider HCP

demographics to provide a more comprehensive understanding of camera use in telehealth for this expanding population of individuals with multimorbidity.

3.5.2. Strengths and limitations

One of the key strengths of this scoping review is its adherence to the JBI methodological framework for scoping reviews (Aromataris et al., 2024), which ensures transparency, rigor, and consistency throughout the research process. By systematically mapping the available evidence, ESR 17's review provides an overview of HCPs perspectives on using cameras in telehealth for older adults. This approach not only identified significant gaps in the literature but also highlighted underexplored areas critical for developing effective telehealth implementation strategies. The findings contribute to advancing knowledge in this emerging field and lay a foundation for future research aimed at addressing these gaps.

Another notable strength lies in the comprehensive search strategy employed. The use of multiple databases (PubMed, CINAHL, Embase, and PsychInfo) alongside additional sources such as citation searches and *ResearchRabbit* ensured a broad and diverse range of studies were captured. This inclusivity enriched the dataset by incorporating perspectives from various disciplines, thereby enhancing the depth and applicability of the findings. Furthermore, the review offers practical insights into tailoring telehealth solutions to meet both patient and provider needs, emphasizing stakeholder engagement as a critical factor in designing effective and acceptable interventions. These findings serve as a valuable resource for researchers, developers, and healthcare providers aiming to optimize telehealth practices for older adults with multimorbidity.

Despite these strengths, several limitations must be acknowledged. A key limitation is linguistic bias. Although no studies were excluded based on language, only one study reviewed was in French, with all others in English. This linguistic homogeneity may restrict cultural and contextual insights into HCP perspectives on telehealth adoption globally. Additionally, the geographical concentration of evidence in six high-income Western countries limits generalisability to regions with differing

healthcare systems. While similar challenges in managing multimorbidity have been observed in other regions (Mechili et al., 2022; Pati et al., 2020), further research is needed to explore HCP perspectives in more diverse contexts.

Another limitation is the absence of formal quality assessment for included studies, consistent with scoping review guidelines (Aromataris et al., 2024). While this aligns with the exploratory nature of scoping reviews, it limits critical appraisal of individual study quality. The use of *ResearchRabbit* as an AI tool to identify potential articles introduces additional concerns regarding selection bias. Only the first 50 studies from its ‘similar works’ feature were screened, which may reflect algorithmic biases in prioritizing articles. Although no additional studies were included through this method, reliance on AI tools raises questions about potential gaps in article selection.

Finally, the broad scope and iterative nature of this review pose challenges for strict reproducibility. While flexibility allowed refinement of search strategies to align with evolving research objectives and capture a wide range of data, it complicates exact replication. Nonetheless, transparency and systematic approaches were prioritized throughout to ensure rigor and reliability.

3.5.3. Future Ethical Considerations

Future research should explore the ethical implications of integrating camera-based technologies into telehealth, particularly concerning patient autonomy, privacy, and the quality of care. As we seek to increasingly consider and rely on digital solutions, it is essential to address how these technologies impact their users. One significant ethical consideration is privacy and data security. The use of camera-based technologies involves collecting and transmitting sensitive visual and audio data, raising concerns about potential breaches and unauthorised access. Research indicates that HCPs face challenges in navigating these risks while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations (Houser et al., 2023).

Future studies should investigate how HCPs navigate these risks while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations. Additionally, exploring patients’ comfort

levels with being filmed in their homes is crucial for balancing clinical needs with respect for personal privacy (Tamara Mujirishvili et al., 2023). Studies have also highlighted the need for HCPs to foster an environment of trust and transparency to the use of telehealth solutions to ensure appropriate and positive engagement (De Hart et al., 2023; Farrer et al., 2022)

Another important area is equity in access to telehealth technologies. Patients with limited digital literacy, cognitive impairments, or financial constraints may encounter barriers to effectively using camera-based systems (Chang et al., 2021; Goldberg et al., 2021; Kalicki et al., 2021). Research should focus on identifying strategies to mitigate these disparities through accessible design, training programs for both patients and HCPs, and policy interventions that promote inclusivity (Chang et al., 2021; Darrat et al., 2021).

The ethical implications of clinical limitations in telehealth should also be considered. The inability to conduct hands-on physical examinations during video consultations may compromise diagnostic accuracy or treatment planning. Future research should examine how HCPs can ethically adapt their practices to address these limitations without compromising on care quality. For instance, the incorporation of alternative methods and the use of technology to enhance patient-provider communication approaches may help bridge this gap (Khan et al., 2022)

Lastly, there is a need to consider HCP workload and well-being. The integration of telehealth technologies could lead to increased administrative tasks and workflow adaptations, which can contribute to further adding strain on HCPs (Houser et al., 2023; Kozikowski et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2023). Investigating ways to ethically distribute these burdens while ensuring adequate support and training for HCPs will be essential.

In conclusion, the ethical implications of integrating camera-based technologies into telehealth are multifaceted, encompassing issues of privacy, equity, clinical limitations, and HCP well-being. Future research should focus on these areas to ensure that telehealth solutions are not only effective but also ethically sound and inclusive.

3.6 Conclusion

ESR17's work highlights the critical role of HCPs in the adoption and integration of camera-based telehealth technologies for managing PwMs. Findings from the scoping review map both the potential benefits and significant challenges associated with these technologies. While telehealth offers opportunities to enhance care coordination, accessibility, and time efficiency, barriers such as technical issues, limited accessibility, and clinical limitations remain significant obstacles. Furthermore, ethical considerations—particularly around privacy, equitable access, and the adequacy of care delivery—are central to ensuring the broader adoption of telehealth solutions.

The review also identifies a notable research gap in understanding HCPs' perspectives on camera-based telehealth technologies, as most existing studies disproportionately focus on patient outcomes. Addressing this gap is essential for developing tailored solutions that align with the needs of both patients and providers. Future research should focus on identifying the specific needs that must be addressed to effectively manage PwMs from an HCP perspective. This includes investigating how camera-based technologies can support care coordination, remote monitoring, and communication while addressing the complexities of managing multiple chronic conditions. Engaging key stakeholders, particularly HCPs, will be essential to explore strategies for overcoming technical and clinical challenges while ensuring equitable access to telehealth technologies. Additionally, ethical concerns such as data security, patient autonomy, and the impact on HCP workload must be carefully addressed to build trust and confidence in these systems.

By addressing these challenges and advancing research on telehealth technologies, healthcare systems would be better positioned to respond to the dual pressures of an aging population and workforce shortages. Importantly, this work underscores the potential of video-based telehealth to address the complex care needs of older adults with multimorbidity by reducing logistical burdens such as frequent

travel for appointments and improving continuity of care through flexible solutions. These advancements could contribute to improving care delivery for older adults across diverse settings.

4. Summary of the Deliverable

This deliverable provides an update on research progress since D3.4 (M29), with a focus on the work of ESR 8 and ESR 17. It examines the use of camera-based Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies to support older adults with multimorbidity at home from two key perspectives: the older adult as the primary end user and healthcare professionals (HCPs) as key facilitators of adoption.

ESR 8's research investigates older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, recognising that their willingness to adopt these solutions is crucial to realising their potential benefits. A key outcome of ESR 8's work is the development of a "future-self intervention," which aims to enhance user acceptance through behaviour change strategies.

ESR 17's research, which commenced in the final year of the project, explores HCPs' perspectives on video-based technologies within telehealth applications. Given the evolving landscape of video-based AAL solutions, understanding HCPs' concerns, expectations, and the real-world applicability of such tools is essential for their successful integration into healthcare practices. A scoping review conducted as part of this research provides the first in-depth analysis of these considerations and directions for future research.

Finally, within Sections 2 and 3 each ESR reflects on privacy and ethical concerns associated with their specific research focus in-home camera use and discusses strategies to support acceptance among both older adults and HCPs, outlining also key implications for the future of camera-based AAL technologies and suggested directions for further research.

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